

Preprint for the article "Performance of Top-of-Rail Products under Contaminated Conditions with Pre-Existing Cracks: Impacts on Traction and Surface Damage"

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Abstract: Top-of-rail (TOR) products are used to optimise friction and reduce wear in the wheel-rail contact. However, their performance is influenced by oxide layers, which naturally cover the rail surface, and contaminants, such as water. Thus, this study used a twin-disc machine to test two types of TOR products: a water-based friction modifier and a grease-based TOR lubricant on clean and oxidised discs in dry and wet conditions. Furthermore, some discs were run-in before testing to create pre-existing surface cracks. Attention was paid to the coefficient of traction (CoT), wear rate and rolling contact fatigue (RCF). Results show that regarding CoT, water affects TOR lubricants more than friction modifiers, as it significantly prolongs their retentivity and causes very low friction (CoT as low as 0.05). While oxides decreased CoT in both dry and wet conditions, they had negligible effects in the presence of TOR products. Both products reduce wear rate effectively and prevent crack formation. However, severe spalling was found when cracks were present before the product application, as water and liquid components of the product accelerated crack propagation. Oxidation had an interesting effect on RCF. It was shown

that not only the disc surfaces but also the crack faces oxidise. This process generates internal pressure that accelerates crack growth without any external load or liquid. On the contrary, it prevents liquid from entering cracks during testing, surpassing the usual mechanism responsible for liquid-induced RCF. This phenomenon opens a new and interesting direction for further research.

Keywords: Friction modification, rolling-contact fatigue, wear, low friction, wheel-rail contact, iron oxides, water

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1. Introduction

In railway operation, top-of-rail (TOR) products are applied to the wheel-rail (W/R) interface to combat adverse effects of friction, such as increased fuel consumption [1], wear and noise [2–7]. Generally, two types of TOR products are used: solid sticks pressed against the wheel [8] or liquid-based suspensions sprayed onto the railhead. Liquid TOR products can be categorised based on their base medium into friction modifiers (water-based) and TOR lubricants (oil- or grease-based) [9]. The difference between these two types is their friction modification mechanisms resulting from their drying/non-drying nature. In friction modifiers (FMs), water acts as the transport medium, carrying solid lubricants along the rail. When it evaporates, it leaves behind a dry layer with low shear strength, typically composed of solid lubricants like graphite or molybdenum disulphide, which reduces friction [10]. On the contrary, due to their oil/grease base, TOR lubricants do not dry out. Instead, they form a thin lubricating film on the rail surface, providing boundary or mixed lubrication regimes [11].

Frictional conditions in the W/R contact are often described by the coefficient of traction (CoT), defined as a ratio between the traction and normal force. Several studies have assessed the effectiveness of TOR products in reducing wear and noise while maintaining sufficient CoT [12–17]. Recently, the possibility of using TOR products to mitigate rolling contact fatigue (RCF) was investigated. RCF is caused by the traction force, which induces minor plastic deformation that accumulates over time. Once the ductility of the material is exhausted, small cracks form in the deformed subsurface layer. These cracks then grow larger until a chunk of the material is removed from the surface, a process known as spalling [18]. Typically, there is competition between wear and RCF, as cracks are

naturally removed due to wear. In some cases, when wear rates are very high, RCF may not develop at all.

Some papers reported the ability of TOR products to prevent crack formation, as they reduce CoT and thus traction force, which results in transition under the plastic shakedown limit to the elastic region in the shakedown map [19–21]. However, a recent study [22] reported results of tests where cracks already existed in the specimen surface before the TOR product was applied. The results showed that although FMs were effective, water and TOR lubricant accelerated the growth of pre-existing cracks, causing massive surface delamination and material loss of up to 1740% compared to dry conditions. The authors identified that the varying effects of different TOR products on RCF and crack growth depend on whether the product is drying or non-drying. In the case of drying products (FMs), water evaporates quickly, leaving only dry particles on the surface. However, for non-drying products (TOR lubricants), the base medium may enter cracks and accelerate their growth due to fluid pressurisation and flank lubrication. The viscosity of the base medium significantly influences this effect, as TOR lubricants with low-viscosity oil have a much more substantial impact on crack growth than those based on high-viscosity grease. In addition, another paper [23] investigated the effect of the liquid amount. In this case, FM was not effective in preventing RCF, and interestingly, the most significant crack growth was observed in so-called "mixed conditions", referring to the situation when FM is almost dried out, so only a negligible amount of fluid is present. Then, the crack growth is enhanced due to the combination of adverse effects of dry friction (high CoT) and the simultaneous presence of liquid.

Based on studies [19–22], it may seem that applying FMs or high-viscosity TOR lubricants presents an effective way of dealing with wear and RCF. However, the study [23]

challenges this as it showed that RCF may develop under FMs, and the reason for that is water contained in their composition. It is important to note that the experiments in the referenced studies are usually conducted under clean conditions without any contaminants. On the actual track, water is often present (e.g. from rain or morning dew), as it is the most common contaminant [24]. It is known that water significantly reduces friction [25–27] and several studies have shown that it can affect the performance of TOR products [28–32]. So, as the evaporation of the base medium of FMs slows down in wet conditions [31] and water reduces the viscosity of TOR lubricants [32], both mechanisms identified in [22] as essential for preventing TOR products from enhancing RCF may be compromised by water.

Depending on the degree of contamination, TOR products may influence RCF differently than in dry and clean conditions, but it is unclear how. Moreover, the state of the wheel and rail surfaces will also play a significant role, as they are naturally subject to oxidation. As the surfaces oxidise, the upper layer turns to a layer of iron oxides with lower shear strength than steel [33]. The crack growth, geometry and capillary forces between the crack face and entrapped liquid will differ in the oxidised layer compared to the conditions tested before, as previous studies used clean and non-oxidised specimens. The need for research on how iron oxides and water combined with TOR products affect wear has been highlighted in [33].

So, in the present study, the effectiveness of two commercial TOR products on reducing wear, RCF and their ability to maintain intermediate CoT was tested. A drying FM and a high-viscosity TOR lubricant (NLGI 0) were selected to address the problems discussed in this chapter. The novelty is that special attention was paid to how water contamination and oxide layer will impact the performance of TOR products. Tests were conducted on

both oxidised and non-oxidised specimens under dry and wet conditions. Additionally, specimens with and without pre-existing cracks were used to evaluate the ability of these products to prevent crack formation. This study addresses whether TOR products can maintain sufficient CoT and effectively mitigate wear and RCF in contact with oxidised surfaces and water contamination, simulating near-field conditions in a laboratory environment.

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2. Material and methods

2.1 Experimental setup

All tests were conducted on a twin-disc machine (MJP-30A, Southwest Jiaotong University) capable of simulating rolling-sliding contact under various conditions. In this setup, the rail disc (mounted on an upper shaft) and wheel disc (mounted on a lower shaft) are driven by separate servo motors, allowing different percentages of slip to be set by varying the speed of both motors, see Fig. 1. The final slip (λ) value in % is a result of the wheel disc running faster than the rail disc and can be calculated as follows:

$$\lambda = \frac{w_{wheel} \cdot r_{wheel} - w_{rail} \cdot r_{rail}}{w_{wheel} \cdot r_{wheel}} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

where w_{wheel} and w_{rail} are angular speeds (r/min) of discs and r_{wheel} and r_{rail} are their radii (mm). Both discs were loaded against each other by a hydraulic loading system. The frictional conditions were quantified in terms of CoT, which can be calculated as follows:

$$CoT = \frac{M_{wheel}}{r_{wheel} \cdot F_N} \quad (2)$$

where M_{wheel} is the torque (N·m) measured on the wheel shaft, r_{wheel} is the wheel disc radius (mm) and F_N stands for the normal force measured by the attached load sensor. The control of all test parameters and data acquisition was performed by the desktop computer connected to the machine.

Fig. 1 Specimens dimensions and the MJP-30A twin-disc machine setup.

The MJP-30A enables testing in various conditions typical for W/R contact. In this study, a Hertz contact pressure of 1.1 GPa was chosen for all experiments, as it is in the range of values typical for contact pressure between the wheel tread and the top of the rail. To achieve 2% slip (a value from the effective part of the traction curve near the saturation point), the mean speed of 1.5 m/s was set (with the wheel disc being slightly faster and the rail disc slightly slower, resulting in the desired slip value). This study carried out two types of tests: "friction tests" and "wear and RCF tests".

2.2 Tested TOR products, contaminants and specimens

One FM and one TOR lubricant were selected for testing to examine both drying and non-drying types of TOR products. The manufacturers do not provide information about the

composition of these products. However, the datasheets for the TOR lubricant indicate that the base is a biodegradable ester oil with a viscosity between 41–53 mm²/s at 40°C. It also contains an organic thickener and soft metal particles. The NLGI grade for this product is "0". The suitable application quantity for a down-scaled twin-disc machine differs from field recommendations. Therefore, preliminary friction tests were conducted to examine the effects of varying application quantities in down-scaled contact. As detailed in the **Results chapter**, the suitable quantities were chosen for each product based on their performance: 20 µl for FM and 10 µl for the TOR lubricant, see **Fig 3**.

Water was applied to the contact in two different ways. In the "friction test" (where CoT was recorded as a function of the number of cycles), water was applied using a pipette in the following quantities: 30 µl, 120 µl and 480 µl. In the case of "wear and RCF tests", water was applied continuously from a drip system hung above the testing machine via a needle at the rate of one drop per second. The number of cycles during which water was fed to the contact is specified in **Tab. 3**.

In "wear and RCF tests", the influence of an oxide layer was investigated. In these tests, specimens were first run-in for 5 000 dry cycles to form pre-existing cracks. After that, the oxidation process was carried out as follows: after the initial run-in, the discs were placed in a chamber preheated at 60 °C for 24 hours, during which vapours from a solution of water, ethanol, and magnesium dichloride induced oxidation. Then, the discs were weighed to quantify the amount of oxide, and the tests were carried out. Please note that the mass of the resulting iron oxide includes both the mass of the original metal and the mass of the oxygen that has been added.

Tab. 1 Chemical composition of specimens materials (wt. %).

Disc	Steel	C	Si	Mn	P	S
Wheel	C-class	0.67–0.77	0.15–1.00	0.60–0.90	0.030	0.005–0.040
Rail	U71Mn	0.65–0.75	0.10–0.50	0.80–1.30	≤0.025	≤0.025

Regarding the specimens, both wheel and rail discs were cut from the actual wheel and rail, respectively. In the case of wheel discs, the material was C-class steel with a hardness of 388 ± 9 HV_{0.5}. Rail discs were made of U71Mn steel with a hardness of 290 HV_{0.5}. The detailed chemical composition of both materials is given in [Tab. 1](#). Furthermore, both discs had the same diameter of 60 mm, and the width of the contact path was 5 mm (linear contact), see [Fig 1](#).

2.3 Test methodology

2.3.1 Friction tests

First, preliminary friction tests without contaminants were performed to select the suitable quantity of FM and TOR lubricant, as the manufacturer's recommendation for field application may not be suitable for down-scaled linear contact in the used apparatus. The amounts tested for FM were 5 μ l, 10 μ l, 20 μ l and 30 μ l and for TOR lubricant: 5 μ l, 10 μ l, 15 μ l. All details are summarised in [Tab. 2](#). Furthermore, the chosen quantity was tested three times to check repeatability. A model friction test is depicted in [Fig. 2 a](#)). The criterion for selecting the optimal amount was that the products provide intermediate CoT levels (green zone) for a reasonable time and do not cause low CoT (red zone).

Fig. 2 a) The "optimal" TOR product performance and b) the wear and RCF tests procedure.

The CoT levels were defined as follows: according to the benchmarking methodology for TOR products [34], the intermediate CoT level, where wear is reduced, but CoT is still sufficient for traction/braking, is defined between $1/3$ and $2/3$ of dry contact CoT. Typical CoT values for dry contact measured on the MJP-30A are between 0.4 and 0.5 [35]. Thus, the intermediate CoT level was defined between 0.15 and 0.3 ($1/3$ and $2/3$ from 0.45 – the middle interval value where CoT stabilises for the dry contact). The value of 0.4, the minimum boundary of the dry contact CoT interval, was considered the threshold at which the product no longer had any significant effect. The test was stopped when this value was reached.

Furthermore, CoT lower than $1/6$ of dry contact CoT is considered low [34], leading to a value of approx. 0.075 under these conditions. Moreover, the study [36] states that a CoT higher than 0.09 is usually required for effective braking. However, the authors don't

specify for which slip % this CoT value is relevant. Thus, this study defined a low CoT level for values lower than 0.1, similar to the previous study [37], to stay conservative on the low CoT definition. Regarding the above-stated intervals for CoT levels, the well-performing TOR product maintains CoT in the 0.15–0.3 interval for as long as possible (marked as "effective retentivity" in Fig. 2 a) and never causes a drop below 0.1. Friction tests are categorised into two groups based on the presence of oxides, see Tab. 2.

Tab. 2 The parameters and conditions of friction tests.

	TOR product; quantity (μl)	Water quantity (μl)	Run-in	Test duration	Slip; speed; pressure	Fig. #
No oxides	–	–	–	500 cycles	2%; 1.5 m/s; 1.1 GPa	3 a)
	–	30, 120, 480	To stable CoT 0.4–0.5	CoT reached 0.4		3 b–d)
	FM; 20 ¹⁾	–				3 i)
	TOR lubricant; 10 ²⁾	–				3 l)
	FM; 20	30, 120, 480				3 j)
TOR lubricant; 10	30, 120, 480	3 m)				
With oxides	–	–	–	500 cycles	2%; 1.5 m/s; 1.1 GPa	3 e)
	–	30, 120, 480	To stable CoT 0.4–0.5 ³⁾	CoT reached 0.4		3 f–h)
	FM; 20	30, 120, 480				3 k)
	TOR lubricant; 10	30, 120, 480				3 n)

- 1) The FM was tested in the following quantities: 5 μl , 10 μl , 15 μl and 20 μl , from which 20 μl was chosen for further testing as it provided the optimal results.
- 2) The TOR lubricant was tested in the following quantities: 5 μl , 10 μl and 15 μl from which 10 μl was chosen for further testing as it provided the optimal results.
- 3) The run-in was conducted before the creation of the oxide layer.

2.3.2 Wear and RCF tests

Tab. 3 The testing parameters and conditions of wear and RCF tests.

	Labeled as	TOR product; quantity (μ l)	TOR product applied when	Water	Pre-existing cracks	Test duration (cycles)	Slip; speed; pressure	Fig. #
No oxides	Test 1	–	–	–	No cracks were present at the time of application	5 000	2%; 1.5 m/s; 1.1 GPa	4 a)
	Test 2	–	–	–		25 000		4 b)
	Test 3	FM; 20	CoT = 0.3	–		25 000		4 c)
	Test 4	TOR lubricant; 10	CoT = 0.3	–		25 000		4 d)
	Test 5	–	–	1 drop/s		25 000		4 e)
	Test 6	FM; 20	CoT = 0.3	–	Run-ins were conducted to form pre-existing cracks	20 000 (+5 000 cycles dry run-in)		4 f)
	Test 7	TOR lubricant; 10	CoT = 0.3	–				4 g)
	Test 8	–	–	1 drop/s				4 h)
	Test 9	FM; 20	Every 600 cycles ¹⁾	1 drop/s				4 i)
	Test 10	TOR lubricant; 10	Every 2 200 cycles ²⁾	1 drop/s				4 j)
With oxides	Test 11	FM; 20	Every 600 cycles ¹⁾	1 drop/s	Run-ins were conducted to form pre-existing cracks	20 000 (+5 000 cycles dry run-in)	9 a)	
	Test 12	TOR lubricant; 10	Every 2 200 cycles ²⁾				9 b)	
	Test 13	–	–				9 c)	

1) FM was applied once every 600 cycles to match the total amount used in the test without water contamination, see 4 c)

2) TOR lubricant was applied once every 2 200 cycles to match the total amount used in the test without water contamination, see 4 d)

Parameters of wear and RCF tests are summarised in [Tab. 3](#), with each test labelled as Test 1–13. The fundamental categorisation of the tests is based on the presence/absence of a pre-prepared oxide layer (as was described in [Subchapter 2.2](#)). Furthermore, 5 000 cycles of dry run-in were conducted in tests 6–13 to create pre-existing cracks, so the ability of TOR products to prevent their formation could be evaluated by comparing tests with and without run-ins. Then, the test started, and depending on the type of the test, the water/TOR product was added either from the beginning or after the initial run-in. TOR products were applied each time CoT reached the value of 0.3, an upper boundary of the intermediate traction level, see [Fig. 2 b](#)). Contrary to friction tests, water was continuously added from a drip system at a rate of 1 drop/s. All test parameters, applied quantity, etc., are summarised in [Tab. 3](#).

In wear and RCF tests, the discs were weighed before and after testing to determine the total mass loss. The wear rate was calculated as the average mass loss normalised per 1 m sliding distance. After the test, discs were sectioned at three different locations (see [Fig. 1](#)), and polished samples were observed via optical (OM) and electron (SEM) microscopes for cracks and other surface damage. Furthermore, energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) was used to analyse whether FM and TOR lubricant can enter the cracks.

3. Results

3.1 Results of friction tests

The results of tests with water without TOR product are depicted in Fig. 3 b–d). It can be seen that with an increase in water amount, the CoT decreases to lower values and recovery time to dry values of CoT is prolonged. Next, the same tests with water were repeated on specimens with an oxide layer, see Fig. 3 f–h). Compared to tests with clean specimens, CoT has now decreased to lower values. However, it can be attributed to the fact that while the CoT for clean specimens stabilises above 0.4, the corresponding value for specimens with an oxide layer is 0.3, see Fig. 3 a) and e). Therefore, the higher decrease in CoT is probably caused by lower initial values, which is also supported by the fact that the drop duration was similar for both types of tests.

In the next step, TOR products in different quantities were tested to choose the optimal dosage. The following quantities were tested: 5 μl , 10 μl , 20 μl , and 30 μl for FM, and 10 μl , 15 μl , and 20 μl for the TOR lubricant. For the FM, 20 μl was selected, as lower quantities did not provide a sufficient duration of effective retentivity. However, increasing the quantity beyond 20 μl did not bring any benefits. After application, the CoT briefly dropped to 0.08, but after a few cycles, the CoT rose to the desired levels. The duration of effective retentivity was approximately 120 cycles. Please note that the "duration of effective retentivity" refers to the number of cycles for which the value of CoT belonged to the intermediate interval, see Fig. 2 a). This test was repeated three times to check the repeatability, see Fig. 3 i).

Fig. 3 a) Dry contact CoT, b–d) Different quantities of water on clean discs, e) Dry oxide layer CoT, f–h) Different amounts of water on oxidised discs, i–k) Tests with FM under various conditions, l–n) Tests with TORL lubricant under different conditions.

Subsequently, the same amount was tested on clean and oxidised specimens under wet conditions, see Fig. 3 j) and k). Water was applied first to wet the surfaces, simulating wet rail conditions. The application of FM followed immediately. On clean specimens, the FM performed similarly to under dry conditions. The duration of the initial drop was slightly

longer, caused by the overflowing of the contact by water. A more significant impact was seen on oxidised specimens when 480 μl of water was applied, resulting in a drop lasting several hundred cycles. However, after the evaporation of water, the product performed similarly to that under dry conditions.

The same tests were conducted for TOR lubricant. Following the same criteria, the quantity of 10 μl was assessed as optimal. TOR lubricants are known to cause over-lubrication when applied in excessive amounts. Although over-lubrication did not occur with any tested quantity, it is expected that in wear and RCF tests, where TOR lubricant is applied repeatedly, TOR lubricant would accumulate over time, preventing CoT recovery, if a higher quantity was selected.

Under wet conditions, the lasting effect was significantly prolonged, see Fig. 3 m). Unlike in the case of FM, the duration now depends substantially on the amount of water. While the CoT recovery took longer under 480 μl of water, the effective retentivity was the longest under 120 μl , suggesting that water can, in specific amounts, enhance the effective retentivity without risk of over-lubrication. Both types of TOR products provided desirable CoT levels in optimal dosage. However, even when applied twice the quantity, the effect of FM was more than four times shorter than that of TOR lubricant. The oxides had no significant impact on the TOR lubricant, see Fig. 3 n).

3.2 Results of wear and RCF tests: No oxides

First, tests 1 and 2 under dry conditions were conducted: the first for 5 000 cycles to check the formation of pre-existing cracks after the run-ins and the second for 25 000 cycles for

comparison with tests with water/TOR products. In these tests, the CoT stabilised in the 0.4–0.5 interval after the initial 2 500 cycles, see Fig. 4 a) and b).

Tests 3–5 were conducted without any run-ins, so water/TOR product was applied right from the beginning. Thus, no major cracks were present on the surface at the moment of application. While FM and TOR lubricant were applied each time the CoT reached 0.3 (resulting in 36 and 10 applications for FM and TOR lubricant, respectively), water was applied continuously with a rate of 1 drop/s, see Fig. 4 c–e). Each application of the TOR product led to a similar CoT curve. Both TOR products were able to provide values from the intermediate CoT level throughout the test, which was achieved with a total amount over 7 times lower for TOR lubricant than for FM. Water maintained stable CoT values between 0.1 and 0.2, see Fig. 4 e). Although those values are not considered optimal, they are still above the low CoT level.

From the friction perspective, there was no significant difference in the performance of TOR products in tests without (3 and 4) and with pre-existing cracks (6 and 7), see Fig. 4 f) and g). However, when comparing tests with water (5 and 8), there is a clear difference in frictional behaviour, see Fig. 4 e) and h). In the first 5 000 cycles of water application, CoT in test 8 had a similar development to that in test 5. But then, CoT gradually rose and became less stable, almost reaching dry contact values at the end of the test. A similar phenomenon, although to a limited extent, was also observed in test 9, where FM was applied together with water, see Fig 4 i). As it was limited to tests where water and pre-existing cracks were present, it is most likely a result of RCF, which will be discussed later. This behaviour was not observed in test 10 with TOR lubricant and water, see Fig. 4 j). Under wet conditions, neither of the TOR products could maintain intermediate CoT.

The combination of water and TOR product caused over-lubrication, and CoT values dropped below 0.1.

Fig. 4 Friction data for wear and RCF tests: No oxides. Tests 1–5 (a–e) were conducted without run-ins. Tests 6–10 (f–j) are with pre-existing cracks. No oxides.

For the wear analysis, specimens were weighed before and after each test to evaluate the mass loss of the wheel disc and rail disc separately. The "total system" represents the combined mass loss of both discs. Fig. 5 a) shows mass loss of discs after tests 1–10 (no oxides). The chart is divided into two parts: tests without pre-existing cracks (1–5) and tests where an initial 5 000 dry cycles were conducted before the water/TOR application to form pre-existing cracks. Fig. 5 b) is divided into two parts in the same way as Fig. 5 a) and displays information about wear rate, which was calculated as total system mass loss per one meter of sliding distance. Please note that, in tests with pre-existing cracks, the initial 5 000 dry cycles were excluded from the evaluation, so the number represents only the part of the test under lubricated conditions.

Fig. 5 a) shows that under dry conditions, the mass loss of the wheel disc is higher than that of the rail discs (tests 1 and 2), but the opposite was true in the rest of the tests. Both TOR products effectively reduce wear, as the total system mass loss decreased 10 times when using FM and 35 times when using the TOR lubricant. In a direct comparison of both products, the TOR lubricant proved to be more than three times as effective as FM in reducing wear. Water achieved similar wear reduction as TOR lubricant, resulting from maintaining low and stable CoT throughout the test and, thus, lower adhesive wear.

The situation changed significantly in tests with pre-existing cracks. The increase in mass loss was observed in all cases, although it is essential to point out that TOR products, when applied to dry surfaces, still provided wear reduction to some extent. Wear rate, calculated as total system mass loss normalised per one meter of sliding distance, is a better indicator of changes in wear intensity in tests 6–10, as it excludes wear during the first 5 000 dry cycles, see Fig. 5 b). The presence of pre-existing cracks and water resulted in an 89 times increase between tests 5 and 8.

Fig. 5 a) Mass loss of wheel disc, rail disc and total system. Part b) shows the total system wear rate in mg per 1 m of sliding distance (run-ins were excluded from the evaluation).

No oxides.

Furthermore, the wear rate in test 8 was three times higher than in dry tests without lubrication (test 2). An increased wear rate was also observed in test 9, where FM was applied together with water. Although it was lower than in test 8, it remained more than six times higher than when FM was used alone (test 6) and more than twice the wear rate under dry conditions. On the contrary, the effect of water was less pronounced in test 10, where TOR lubricant was used, suggesting that wet conditions influence TOR products differently depending on their base medium type.

Tests without pre-existing cracks

Tests with pre-existing cracks

Fig. 6 OM pictures of the surface after testing. No oxides.

After mass loss/wear rate evaluation, surfaces were observed under an optical microscope, see Fig. 6. OM analysis showed signs of minor spalling in tests 3 and 4 but no visible cracks, meaning that both TOR products were more or less effective in preventing crack

initiation. However, surfaces in tests with pre-existing cracks exhibited severe spalling and extensive cracking, with the most pronounced damage observed in tests 8, 9, and 10, where water was present.

Fig. 7 RCF crack parameters: a) length and b) depth. Tests without and with pre-existing cracks are displayed in separate figures. No oxides.

As the wear and RCF were more severe for the rail discs (see Fig. 5), and the wheel discs often showed no noticeable cracks, the following crack analysis will focus only on the rail discs, which are of greater interest. After 5 000 and 25 000 dry cycles, the surfaces showed signs of adhesive wear and minor spalling (see Fig. 6, tests 1 and 2). The black areas represent material peeled off the original surface and then adhered to a different location. As shown in Fig. 7), the median length and depth of cracks were similar in these tests,

suggesting that 5 000 cycles of running-in are sufficient to create pre-existing cracks. **Fig. 8 a)** shows that cracks run parallel to the surface, entering at an average angle of around 10 degrees.

The cracks observed in tests 4 and 5, where water and TOR lubricant were used, were very short and shallow and ran under an average angle of around 12 degrees. Only a few turned towards the bulk under a steep 25–50 degrees angle. In contrast, the cracks in test 3 with FM ran under a much smaller angle of 6 degrees and were similar in size to those observed under dry conditions.

Regarding tests with TOR products and pre-existing cracks (**Fig. 8 b and c**), the final length and depth of cracks were somewhat similar to tests without pre-existing cracks. However, there was a substantial difference when TOR products were applied in wet conditions (**Fig. 8 e–h**), as the length of the cracks in test 10 was, on average, almost 58 times longer than in test 4, and their depth increased 94 times. There was an even more significant change in the case of water alone, where cracks in test 8 were, on average, more than 200 times longer and more than 150 times deeper than in test 5. Numerous cracks were found running above one another, causing extensive material peeling. These cracks entered the surface at a shallow angle at first, similar to earlier tests, but then turned towards the bulk and propagated at a much steeper angle, reaching depths of nearly 600 μm , see **Fig. 8 d**).

Fig. 8 SEM pictures of cracks: a) Dry 25 000 cycles, b) FM (with pre-existing cracks), c) TOR lubricant (with pre-existing cracks), d) Water (with pre-existing cracks), e) and f) FM in wet conditions (with pre-existing cracks), g) and h) TOR lubricant in wet conditions (with pre-existing cracks). No oxides.

Fig. 8 presents SEM images of typical cracks observed in cross-sections from tests 6–10. In tests where water was present (8–10), the cracks propagated deep into the bulk material, exhibiting branching and coalescence. In contrast, in tests 6 and 7, the cracks remained shallow. So, water was able to enter cracks and played a crucial role in crack propagation. In addition, an EDS analysis was conducted to confirm whether TOR products can also enter cracks. As a result, EDS detected carbon particles inside the cracks (see **Fig. 8 b**) and **f**). The only possible carbon source was the FM, which usually contains graphite or carboxymethyl cellulose (although authors do not know the exact composition of used TOR products, EDS analysis confirmed carbon as one of the constituents of FM). It is important to note that although the steel used for the discs also contains a trace

amount of carbon, it was likely too low to form the thick black coating observed on the crack faces.

3.3 Results of wear and RCF tests: With oxides

Fig. 9 Friction data for wear and RCF tests: With oxides. All tests were conducted on specimens with pre-existing cracks. a) FM and water, b) TOR lubricant and water, c) water.

In tests 11–13, specimens were first run-in for 5 000 cycles to create pre-existing cracks. After that, both discs were put in a climate chamber for 24 hours to form an oxide layer. Then, the test was conducted the same way as in tests 8–10. Regarding friction, CoT measured in tests where TOR products were applied on oxidised specimens stayed in the same range as in tests where clean specimens were used (9 and 10). For FM, this range was between 0.1–0.15, see Fig. 9 a). For TOR lubricant, CoT values were slightly lower, as they stayed below 0.1 for most of the test, see Fig. 9 b). However, a difference was observed in tests with water, as the CoT now remained stable around 0.2, unlike in test 8, where

CoT gradually increased to values approaching dry contact friction (see Fig. 4 h). This behaviour resembled test 5 (Fig. 4 e), where water was used, but no pre-existing cracks were present. This suggests that, from a frictional perspective, an oxide layer suppresses the influence of pre-existing cracks, allowing water to affect CoT like in conditions without cracks.

Fig. 10 a) Mass loss of wheel disc, rail disc and total system. Part b) shows the total system wear rate in milligrams per 1 m of sliding distance (run-ins were excluded from the evaluation). Specimens with an oxide layer.

Specimens were weighed before and after the test to evaluate the mass loss and wear rate. However, it is essential to note that it was impossible to distinguish between the mass loss of the oxides and the bulk steel. As the oxide layer has lower shear strength than steel and is easily worn, the mass loss and wear rate calculated for specimens with oxides could not be meaningfully compared to the wear rate of the specimens in the previous tests without oxides. This is evident from comparing tests 11 and 12 with tests 9 and 10, respectively. These tests show that higher mass loss and wear rate were measured for specimens with an oxide layer (see Fig. 10 a) and b) than for those without oxides (see Fig. 5 a) and b). The

exception was test 13 with water, where the measured mass loss and wear rate of specimens with an oxide layer were lower than in test 8 without oxides, which will be discussed later in the [Discussion section](#).

Fig. 11 OM pictures of the surface after testing. No oxides.

The unworn oxide layer can be seen in [Fig. 11](#), with its thickness and cross-section visible in SEM images in [Fig. 12 a–d](#)). SEM images show that the oxides uniformly covered the surface in a layer with thicknesses varying in the order of micrometres. After the tests, OM observation of the surface did not reveal any major signs of RCF. The oxide layer was visibly worn, and several pits were found, most likely due to peeled-off oxides or bulk material (see [Fig. 11](#)). The pre-existing cracks are visible in cross-section images in [Fig. 12 a–d](#)). After testing, crack measurements revealed that their parameters were comparable to those in tests under dry conditions, despite expectations that water or the combination of water and TOR product would enhance crack growth like in previous cases, see [Fig. 13 a](#)) and [b](#)). A possible explanation for why discs with oxides did not experience

severe RCF as in the case with clean specimens will be discussed next in the **Discussion** section.

Fig. 12 SEM pictures: a–d) intact oxide layer before testing, e) after test with FM and water, f) TOR lubricant and water, g) water, h) detail on deformed material. Tests with oxides and pre-existing cracks.

Fig. 13 Crack parameters: a) length and b) depth. Tests with oxides and pre-existing cracks.

4 Discussion

4.1 Tests without oxides

In this study, the authors used the interval application of TOR products. Although smart application units that control lubricant applications based on real-time friction data have recently been implemented, interval application remains the dominant method. In this approach, TOR products are applied after a certain number of vehicle passes or a fixed time interval, regardless of weather conditions. Thus, over-lubrication due to lubricant accumulation or contamination is more likely, as was the case in this study. As suggested in [23], potentially interesting phenomena may be observed if the water/TOR product application is less frequent and starvation occurs, requiring application not in fixed intervals but instead depending more on actual CoT data. The author used interval application to examine the worst-case scenario from the point of traction/adhesion problems that may occur on track. From the perspective of future research, the authors will focus on what happens when contact starves, and CoT reaches higher values, approaching dry contact, as it may reveal interesting phenomena. While this aspect is undoubtedly relevant, addressing it in the present study would go beyond its intended scope, making it a natural subject for future investigation.

Problems with over-lubrication did not occur after a single water application in any of the friction tests. However, the situation changed when water was continuously applied in wear and RCF tests. Although water also affected FM somewhat, the results with TOR lubricant were more interesting, see Fig. 4 j). CoT reached the lowest values in this test, staying between 0.05 and 0.07, as the water stopped its recovery. This indicates that TOR lubricants may cause over-lubrication even in recommended dosages when used under wet

conditions. A possible explanation may be based on studies describing water–oil/grease interactions, which explain that combining water and grease may lead to a better lubrication effect [38–40]. Several studies suggest that some thickeners are able to absorb water, which may lower grease viscosity and enhance contact replenishment [41–43]. Furthermore, the manufacturer lists an organic thickener, and the formulation appears consistent with a polyurea-based system commonly used in the industry. Polyurea greases, particularly those based on biodegradable esters, can emulsify water up to several per cent and, under intense mixing, absorb as much as 70–80% of water without losing structural integrity. This remarkable water uptake likely accounts for the prolonged period of low traction coefficient ("over-lubricated" state) observed during continuous wetting in the TOR lubricant tests. However, a more detailed understanding of the water absorption behaviour would require additional testing, which was beyond the scope of this study. Such testing could include the construction of a water uptake curve using standardised methods such as ASTM D4049 (spray test) or ASTM D7342 (Karl-Fischer titration) to track moisture content over time. Polyurea/ester-based greases absorb up to approximately 5–10 wt% of water under mild exposure and considerably more under blending conditions.

Now, the effect of pre-existing cracks will be discussed. FM reduced the wear rate in tests without pre-existing cracks by 10 times (test 3), while the TOR lubricant achieved a 35 times reduction (test 4). Meanwhile, water in test 5 led to a 29 times reduction compared to dry conditions, see Fig. 5 b). FM achieved worse wear reduction than TOR lubricant as it repeatedly dried out, causing an increase in CoT and, consequently, higher adhesive wear. In contrast, water maintained a stable and low CoT. Although the TOR lubricant also periodically reached a CoT of 0.3 like FM, it exhibited a longer-lasting effect than FM,

providing a lower CoT for an extended period. Overall, it can be said that both TOR products were effective in reducing wear, and no significant signs of RCF were found, but TOR lubricant was more effective.

In tests with pre-existing cracks, all aspects of RCF increased substantially. A crack length and depth comparison with previous tests showed that a liquid base of both TOR products accelerated crack growth (see Fig 7 a). However, water on its own had an even more significant effect on RCF, as under these conditions, the crack depth and length were an order of magnitude higher than under TOR products. In reality, cracks are always present in the rail surface. Thus, applying TOR products may severely impact rail service life, which may not be apparent from testing in laboratory conditions if new specimens without cracks are used for testing. Thus, more interest should be placed on testing specimens with pre-existing cracks and surface damage. These findings follow the study [22], where a similar change in RCF behaviour was observed when pre-existing cracks were present, but for different material pairs and TOR products than used in this study.

The behaviour of TOR products under wet conditions from the perspective of RCF has not been studied yet. Tests 9 and 10 showed that crack lengths were up to five times longer under FM in wet conditions than in tests where FM was applied in dry conditions, and in some cases, cracks propagated up to ten times deeper beneath the surface. The combination of water and TOR lubricant accelerated crack growth even further, reaching depths of up to 900 μm (see Fig. 7 b), the deepest from all tests. Those cracks and signs of spalling were visible to the naked eye (Fig. 6), showing that TOR products affect RCF differently in wet than dry conditions. In the case of FM, it was more likely water that caused RCF. FM could not prevent it, as it is dissolvable in water, and the mass loss was similar to water-only conditions. Instead of drying out, the base medium of FM remains

liquid and, together with water, enters cracks, accelerating their growth due to crack face lubrication and hydropressurization mechanisms [44].

However, in the case of TOR lubricant, the situation appears more complicated, as it is unclear whether it can enter a crack due to its viscosity. EDS detected carbon particles inside the cracks for FM but not for TOR lubricant. However, since water may influence grease and enhance replenishment, as stated in [41–43], it could be easier for bleed oil of TOR lubricant to enter a crack under wet conditions, which EDS would not detect. In that case, crack faces would be well-lubricated (as CoT decreases as low as 0.05). Thus, internal friction would be very low, and cracks could easily propagate. Usually, if the friction between the crack faces is lower than 0.2, cyclic shear crack growth may occur [45]. The CoT was considerably below this value. In addition, any trapped liquid (TOR lubricant, its bleed oil or water) becomes pressurised by load and causes a phenomenon similar to the oil wedge effect [46]. As evident from test 10, the combination of TOR lubricant and water accelerated crack growth the most, as cracks penetrated the deepest into the bulk. However, this was not reflected in the wear rate, likely because the cracks propagated almost perpendicularly to the surface and did not connect with it. As a result, material removal was limited, and only minor spalling was observed. If the test had been extended, substantial spalling would be expected to occur.

4.3 The effect of oxides

The three most common iron oxides are wustite, hematite (red oxide), and magnetite (black oxide), along with their hydrated versions (rusts). Hematite can be commonly found on the rail surface, forming a brittle layer that can easily break, and the worn particles cause abrasion, leaving scars on the surfaces [33]. In this study, authors used a modified

approach proposed by Sone [47], which was also adopted in several other studies [48–51]. It consists of several steps in which specimens are alternately exposed to low and high-humidity air at 40°C using a NaCl solution. As a result, the entire surface was covered with a thick, uniform oxide layer (see Fig. 14). Although the objective was primarily to create hematite, the final layer likely consisted of a mixture of hematite and rust.

Studies often report that hematite increases friction [52]. However, this was not observed in any of tests, where it caused a reduction in CoT from 0.4 to 0.3. This inconsistency may be explained by air humidity. A study [53] showed that when hematite is mixed with water, the mixture's viscosity increases exponentially with solid particle content. This mixture then causes low friction, likely because hematite particles are strong enough to carry the load but have low shear strength, allowing them to act as an effective lubricant. This was further confirmed in another study [54], where the shear strength of a hematite and FM mixture was measured. So, while hematite increases friction in dry conditions, the opposite seems to be true in wet conditions [33]. The high humidity in the laboratory (although not explicitly measured) may have caused water condensation during experiments. Water was then mixed with the oxides, explaining why hematite caused a decrease in CoT rather than an increase.

The effect of oxides on friction has been well examined in many studies [48–51], but their impact on wear and RCF is still unclear [33]. Depending on the lubricant used, the total mass loss in tests with oxides was significantly higher than in tests with TOR products in dry conditions on clean discs. However, despite the presence of water, the total mass loss was more than three times lower than on clean discs, suggesting that while oxides accelerate wear, they somehow prevent RCF.

Fig. 14 Picture of a disc after oxide treatment and an OM detail on the surface.

In **Fig. 12**, SEM images of cross-sections show that the oxide layer was several microns thick. More importantly, it was observed that the crack faces were also oxidised. As the oxides grow bigger, they fill the insides of cracks and separate their faces. At some point, the oxides start to pressure internal surfaces, similar to the hydropressurisation caused by fluids. This process occurs during oxidation, so the crack growth is accelerated even before any testing is conducted. This is supported by the fact that some cracks found after the oxide treatment were significantly larger than those typically created during the run-in, with the oxide being the likely cause. However, this hypothesis is based on a simple observation and has not been thoroughly analysed. Once the oxides fill the cracks, they prevent fluids from entering. This means that water or TOR products cannot go inside, and mechanisms such as face lubrication or hydropressurisation cannot occur. As a result, cracks did not grow further during testing, even though liquid was on the surface.

Oxides have low shear strength, so the top layer was quickly worn, meaning cracks could not grow and were also worn. This can be seen in **Fig. 12**, where images **a–d**) show the surface and cracks before the test, and **e–h**) show the surface after the test. After testing,

the surface was very smooth, with only small pits in areas where oxides or cracks were previously present before being worn off. An interesting phenomenon is observed in Fig. 12 h), where a crack with an unusual shape was detected. The corrosive solution was sprayed on the crosssectioned surface to highlight the deformation lines around this crack (see the detail in Fig. 12 h). Deformation lines are visible on one side of the crack but absent on the other. A possible explanation is that this is not an RCF crack but rather a piece of material initially located on the left side in an upward position. A hole formed next to it due to oxidic wear, and this material was deformed by traction forces and indented into the hole left by the worn oxides. Similar behaviour was also observed in [55].

The effect of oxides can be summarised as follows. Oxides enhance crack propagation even before the start of the test by exerting pressure on internal faces. However, they also block any liquid from entering, preventing usual mechanisms responsible for further crack growth. As the top layer is easily worn due to its low shear strength, the result is smooth surfaces without any apparent cracks, see Fig 12 e–h). Thus, RCF is less likely to occur on oxidised surfaces.

5 Conclusion

This study investigated whether TOR products can effectively reduce wear and prevent rolling contact fatigue (RCF) while maintaining an intermediate coefficient of traction (CoT) in the presence of contaminants typically found on the railhead. All tests were conducted on a twin-disc machine, using conditions representative of wheel-rail (W/R) contact. Two types of TOR products were selected: a water-based friction modifier (FM) and a grease-based TOR lubricant, allowing for a comparison between drying and non-drying compositions. Specimens were cut from authentic materials, and some of them were run-in to create pre-existing surface cracks. Given its significant impact on traction and braking, water was chosen as the primary contaminant. Additionally, some discs underwent an oxidation treatment to form an oxide layer on the surface, enabling an examination of the influence of third-body layers on RCF and wear.

From the perspective of CoT, the results can be summarised as follows. Water influenced both TOR products differently. In the case of FM, water delayed the evaporation of the base medium, prolonging friction-modifying effects. For the TOR lubricant, the impact on retentivity was even more substantial. Over-lubrication was observed in tests with repeated applications, primarily due to the product accumulation over time and as the result of thickener absorbing water. This led to conditions of extremely low friction, with CoT values dropping as low as 0.05 – a value considered insufficient for safe railway vehicle operation. The oxide layer decreased CoT in dry and wet conditions, but the effect was negligible in the presence of TOR product.

Adhesive wear was the dominant wear mechanism observed under dry conditions. Both TOR products effectively reduced wear rate, with the TOR lubricant proving the most

efficient. The FM was less effective, likely due to its tendency to dry quickly. Both products effectively prevent crack formation and reduce mass loss. However, in tests where cracks were formed before the application of products, severe RCF was observed as the liquid component of products accelerated crack propagation due to crack face lubrication and hydropressurisation. RCF damage intensified when TOR products were contaminated by water. The combined effect of FM and water resulted in significant mass loss, whereas TOR lubricant, though not experiencing as high mass loss, exhibited deeper crack penetration. These deeper cracks posed a risk of substantial spalling if allowed to merge, which would possibly happen if the test duration was prolonged.

An interesting phenomenon was found in tests with oxidised specimens. It was observed that the crack faces also oxidise. As the oxides grow, they fill the crack interior, creating pressure and initiating crack propagation. This effect resembled hydropressurisation but occurred under dry conditions without any external load. Furthermore, water or liquid components of TOR products could not enter cracks due to oxides suppressing the usual mechanisms of liquid-driven crack propagation. And, as the oxidised surface is easily worn due to the low shear strength of oxides, the cracks were quickly removed, leaving a smooth surface after testing with no signs of RCF.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly and ChatGPT in order to improve the language quality and increase readability. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Credit Author Statement

Simon Skurka: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft. **Radovan Galas:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Jiaxin Li:** Methodology, Investigation. **Honghao Wang:** Methodology, Investigation. **Milan Omasta:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing, Project administration. **Haohao Ding:** Writing - review & editing. **Wenjian Wang:** Project administration. **Ivan Krupka:** Data curation, Writing - review & editing. **Martin Hartl:** Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the repository

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